

ISic1530

I.Sicily inscription 1530

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (blue)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 158

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [X]ρυσίς χρηστή
2. χρησιανή Χρ(ιστόν)
3. πιστεύσασα
4. [ἔζ]ησεν ἔτη
5. ιη κατέθετο

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645030

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.34
Ferrua, A 1940. Nuovi studi nelle catacombe di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia
Cristiana*. 17: 43-81. At 71

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